

1 **Cardiopulmonary Mortality and Fine Particulate Air Pollution**
2 **by Species and Source in a National U.S. Cohort**

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46 **Abstract**

47 The purpose of this study was to estimate cardiopulmonary mortality associations for
48 long-term exposure to PM_{2.5} species and sources (i.e., components) within the U.S. National
49 Health Interview Survey cohort. Exposures were estimated through a chemical transport
50 model for six species (i.e., elemental carbon [EC], primary organic aerosols [POA],
51 secondary organic aerosols [SOA], sulfate [SO₄], ammonium [NO₃], nitrate [NH₄]) and five
52 sources of PM_{2.5} (i.e., vehicles, electricity generating units [EGU], non-EGU industrial
53 sources, biogenic sources [bio], “other” sources). In single-pollutant models, we found
54 positive, significant ($p < 0.05$) mortality associations for all components, except POA. After
55 adjusting for remaining PM_{2.5} (total PM_{2.5} minus component), we found significant mortality
56 associations for EC (hazard ratio [HR] = 1.36; 95% CI: [1.12, 1.64]), SOA (HR = 1.11; 95%
57 CI: [1.05, 1.17]), and vehicle sources (HR = 1.06; 95% CI: [1.03, 1.10]). HRs for EC, SOA,
58 and vehicle sources were significantly larger than for remaining PM_{2.5} (per unit $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). Our
59 findings suggest that cardiopulmonary mortality associations vary by species and source,
60 with evidence that EC, SOA, and vehicle sources are important contributors to the PM_{2.5}
61 mortality relationship. With further validation, these findings could facilitate targeted
62 pollution regulations that more efficiently reduce air pollution mortality.

63 **Keywords:** air pollution, cardiopulmonary mortality, species, source, cohort study

64 **Synopsis:** This study provides evidence that cardiopulmonary mortality associations vary
65 among PM_{2.5} species and sources, suggesting that pollution regulations could be improved by
66 targeting relatively harmful particulate air pollutants.

67 **Introduction**

68 Air pollution has been estimated as the fourth largest contributor to global burden of
69 disease.¹ Specifically, cardiopulmonary mortality has consistently been associated with fine
70 particulate air pollution (PM_{2.5}).²⁻⁴ PM_{2.5} is comprised of a complex mixture of chemical
71 species, each potentially having different effects on mortality. Mortality associations have
72 also been found to vary across PM_{2.5} sources,^{5,6} which could be driven by differences in
73 particle mass, number, size, shape, surface area, or chemical composition. Thus, targeting
74 relatively harmful components (i.e., species or sources) may be more beneficial than simply
75 reducing total PM_{2.5}. Current regulations, however, focus on total PM_{2.5}, in part due to
76 uncertainty of component-specific toxicities.

77 Despite general interest, a limited number of cohort studies have estimated component-
78 specific mortality associations, in part due to difficulties modelling exposures. A few early
79 cohort studies estimated mortality relationships for sulfates,^{7,8} but only recently has a more
80 comprehensive spectrum of species and sources been considered.^{5,9} Moreover, results of
81 past studies have been somewhat inconsistent, establishing the need for additional analysis.

82 The purpose of this study was to estimate component-specific mortality associations for
83 long-term exposure to PM_{2.5} species and sources. Speciated and source-apportioned PM_{2.5}
84 exposure estimates were linked to a cohort of >160,000 adults living in metropolitan
85 statistical areas (MSAs) across the U.S. Within this cohort, cardiopulmonary mortality
86 associations were estimated for six chemical species (i.e., elemental carbon [EC], primary
87 organic aerosols [POA], secondary organic aerosols [SOA], sulfates [SO₄], ammonium
88 [NH₄], and nitrates [NO₃]) and five sources of PM_{2.5} (i.e., vehicles, electricity generating
89 units [EGU], non-EGU industrial sources, biogenic sources [bio], and “other” sources). A

90 secondary aim of this analysis was to determine if cardiopulmonary mortality associations
91 differ between primary (i.e., fine particles emitted directly from sources) and secondary
92 PM_{2.5} (i.e., fine particles formed from atmospheric oxidation of gaseous precursors). As
93 such, we separated primary (i.e., EC and POA) and secondary species (i.e., SOA, SO₄, NH₄,
94 and NO₃) within PM_{2.5} sources to estimate relative mortality associations.

96 **Methods**

97 *Study Population Data:*

98 For this analysis, a cohort was constructed of adults who participated in the U.S. National
99 Health Interview Survey (NHIS). The NHIS is an annual cross-sectional survey that
100 provides a representative sample of the civilian noninstitutionalized U.S. population. NHIS
101 data are collected continuously throughout each survey year by the U.S. Census Bureau
102 through in-person and telephone interviews. Public use NHIS survey data from 1986 to
103 2001 were linked to the National Death Index, providing mortality follow-up through
104 December 31, 2015. A detailed description of NHIS sample design, interview procedures,
105 and data access can be found elsewhere.^{10, 11}

106 Several exclusion criteria limited the size and determined the composition of the analytic
107 cohort. Merging individuals to exposure estimates required residential data, which were
108 available only at the MSA-level and for individuals surveyed before 2002 (n = 587,100
109 remaining). Limited smoking and BMI data further reduced cohort size (n = 198,955
110 remaining), resulting in the exclusion of anyone surveyed in 1986, 1989, or 1996.
111 Individuals missing information on any other covariate were also excluded. After

112 exclusions, the analytic cohort consisted of 164,291 adults living within NHIS-sampled
113 MSAs.

114

115 *Air Pollution Data:*

116 Exposure estimates for PM_{2.5} species and sources were developed via a blending of
117 simulated and empirical data. Speciated and source-apportioned concentrations for 2001 and
118 2010 were derived from chemical transport model (CTM) simulations, with bias corrections
119 to better match speciated monitor data.

120 A brief description of the CTM simulations follows, with details documented
121 elsewhere.¹² We used the PMCAMx model¹³⁻¹⁶ and the “source tagging” algorithm PSAT¹⁷⁻
122 ²¹ to estimate species and source concentrations. PMCAMx simulates chemical reactions in
123 the gas, aqueous, and particulate phases, with an advanced treatment of organic PM_{2.5} that
124 accounts for the semi-volatile nature of primary organic emissions and incorporates recent
125 advances in secondary organic PM chemistry.²²⁻²⁴ Simulations were performed using an
126 internally consistent set of 2001 and 2010 emissions inventories, developed by Xing et al.²⁵
127 Emissions inventories were constructed from several activity and emission control
128 databases, including the State Energy Data System, National Emissions Inventory trends
129 report, and 2011 National Transportation Statistics.²⁵ Meteorological data used in PMCAMx
130 were taken from simulations performed with the Weather Research Forecasting model
131 (WRF v3.6.1).

132 The PMCAMx model domain covered the continental United States at a horizontal
133 resolution of 36 kilometers. While coarse, a 36-kilometer resolution was necessary to
134 maintain computational feasibility. Additionally, increasing simulation resolution from 36 x

135 36 to 1 x 1 kilometer grids in a major city (i.e., Pittsburgh) had minimal effect on predicted
136 exposures (less than 3%).²⁶

137 Species predicted by the model and used in the health analysis included EC, POA, SOA,
138 SO₄, NH₄, and NO₃. These species were selected as they are major contributors to total
139 PM_{2.5} and were reliably estimated. Concentrations of sodium, chloride, and mineral dust
140 were also estimated, but not used in the health analysis due to low concentrations or lack of
141 speciated monitor data.

142 Source categories were necessarily identical to those from the emissions inventories used
143 as inputs to the CTM.²⁵ While PM_{2.5} source categories could be defined in a variety of ways,
144 the categories used in this study reflect sources that have traditionally been most relevant for
145 regulatory purposes. The EGU category represents emissions from electricity-generating
146 units included in the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency's Integrated Planning Model.
147 Non-EGU includes all other industrial point sources. Vehicles includes emissions from on-
148 road vehicles in the U.S. and off-road vehicles in the entire domain. Biogenic includes
149 emissions from vegetation. The "other" source includes on-road vehicles from Canada and
150 Mexico plus all other emissions.

151 As with most CTM simulations, the concentrations directly predicted by PMCAMx
152 exhibited systematic regional biases. Therefore, speciated PM_{2.5} concentrations predicted by
153 PMCAMx were adjusted using geographically weighted regression²⁷ to better match
154 speciated monitor data.^{28, 29} For each species, a separate regression was used to predict the
155 bias between CTM predictions and observed concentrations. Regression predictor variables
156 included speciated CTM concentrations, inverse distance to nearest urban area, average
157 monitor elevation difference, and local bias between CTM and empirically modelled PM_{2.5}.

158 Pollution monitor observations were weighted using a Gaussian function that decays with
159 distance. Bias predictions were made at the census-tract level to allow for finer resolution
160 corrections in areas with higher population density. The CTM fields were then corrected
161 based on predicted biases for each census tract and species. During this process, the
162 fractional source apportionment for individual species was assumed to be constant.²⁶

163 In addition to component-specific exposures, multiple estimates of total PM_{2.5} exposure
164 were used in this analysis. One estimate of total PM_{2.5} exposure was defined as the sum of
165 speciated concentrations (i.e., PM_{2.5} CTM '01, '10). An additional estimate of PM_{2.5}
166 exposure (i.e., PM_{2.5} IEG '01, '10) was predicted using an integrated empirical geographic
167 (IEG) model, which applies pollution monitor measurements within a universal kriging
168 framework.³⁰ While many IEG model inputs were temporally fixed, year-to-year trends and
169 variations were accounted for through temporally variable land use data and satellite-derived
170 pollution estimates.³⁰

171 Census tract level exposure estimates for PM_{2.5} and components were aggregated to the
172 MSA-level as a population weighted average. Details on how MSA borders were defined in
173 the aggregation process are provided in Supporting Information Appendix A. Individual
174 exposures were assigned, based on residence at time of survey, as the simple average of
175 2001 and 2010 MSA-level concentration estimates. To assess the impacts of using only two
176 annual concentration estimates, an additional measure of total PM_{2.5} was constructed as the
177 average of annual, IEG-modelled PM_{2.5} from 1999-2015 (i.e., PM_{2.5} IEG '99-'15).

178 *Mortality Risk Analysis:*

179 Cardiopulmonary mortality associations were quantified as adjusted hazard ratios (HRs)
180 from Cox proportional hazards models (PHREG procedure in SAS; version 9.4; SAS
181 Institute Inc.). Concentration-response curves were not estimated, as a previous analysis
182 with the NHIS cohort found that the concentration-response relationship between PM_{2.5} and
183 cardiopulmonary mortality was approximately linear.²

184 Cardiopulmonary mortality was defined, based on the tenth revision of the International
185 Classification of Diseases (ICD-10), to include deaths from cardiovascular disease (ICD-10
186 codes: I00-I09, I11, I13, I20-I51), cerebrovascular disease (I60-I69), chronic lower
187 respiratory disease (J40-J47), and influenza or pneumonia (J09-J18). Causes of death
188 corresponding to the preceding ICD-10 codes are specified in Table S1. For
189 cardiopulmonary mortality, survival times were calculated as the difference between year of
190 death and survey year. Otherwise, survival times were censored at date of non-
191 cardiopulmonary mortality or end of follow-up (i.e., 2015).

192 Control variables were chosen *a priori* based on past research conducted with the NHIS
193 cohort.^{2, 31} The following control variables were used in each model. Age, sex, and race-
194 ethnicity were controlled for by allowing each combination of age (one year), sex, and race-
195 ethnicity, to be assigned their own baseline hazard (using the STRATA statement of the
196 PHREG procedure in SAS). Models also included categorical variables for family income
197 (\$0-35,000; \$35,000-50,000; \$50,000-75,000; > \$75,000); marital status (married, divorced,
198 separated, never married, widowed); educational attainment (less than high school graduate,
199 high school graduate, some college, college graduate, more than college graduate); BMI
200 (<20, 20-25, 25-30, 30-35, >35 kg/m²); smoking status (current, former, never); census

201 region (Northeast, South, Midwest, West); and survey year. For details on how control
202 variables were harmonized across survey years, see Supporting Information Appendix B.

203 While control variables were consistent across models, specifications differed in how
204 they accounted for relationships between PM_{2.5} components. Single-pollutant models
205 included all control variables along with a single component of PM_{2.5}. This approach
206 provides greater statistical power as it is less affected by multi-collinearity, yet it yields
207 inherently biased estimates due to component correlation with total PM_{2.5}. Mass-adjusted
208 models addressed this issue by including remaining PM_{2.5} (i.e., CTM predicted total PM_{2.5}
209 minus PM_{2.5} component). Moreover, mass-adjusted models provide a formal structure for
210 estimating the likelihood that mortality associations differ between components. That is, for
211 each component a Wald hypothesis test was conducted, with the null hypothesis that
212 component and remaining PM_{2.5} HRs were equivalent.

213 Mortality associations were also estimated for primary and secondary PM_{2.5}, within
214 sources. While several source categories were almost entirely primary or secondary, total
215 PM_{2.5}, vehicle sources, and “other” sources had sizable portions of both primary and
216 secondary species. Thus, only total PM_{2.5}, vehicle sources, and “other” sources were
217 separated into primary and secondary species. Source-specific primary PM_{2.5} was defined as
218 the sum of EC and POA from a given source, whereas secondary PM_{2.5} was defined as the
219 sum of SOA, SO₄, NH₄, and NO₃. Single-pollutant models were estimated, along with a
220 two-pollutant model that separately included primary and secondary PM_{2.5} from a given
221 source (e.g., primary vehicles and secondary vehicles).

222 In all cases, pollution exposures were measured in micrograms per cubic meter (μg/m³)
223 and modelled as continuous variables. Exposures were scaled such that HRs were relative to

224 either a unit or mean $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ increase in exposure. When scaled per unit, HRs more
225 accurately reflect relative toxicities, especially after adjusting for remaining $\text{PM}_{2.5}$. Scaling
226 exposures per mean incorporates a component's relative contribution to total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and
227 accounts for differential scaling bias in single-pollutant models.

228

229 **Results**

230 *Data Summary:*

231 Individuals within our cohort were predominantly female (56.6%), white non-Hispanic
232 (66%), married (50.8%), high-school graduates (30.7%), and never smokers (51.7%) (Table
233 1). Figure S1 maps pollution exposure estimates for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass and components across
234 NHIS surveyed MSAs, displaying the spatial distribution of exposures. Spatial variation for
235 some components (e.g., EGU and SO_4) was mostly regional, which reduced statistical power
236 when controlling for census region. Additionally, Figure 1 depicts the relative species
237 composition of each source. Some sources (e.g., bio) were primarily comprised of a single
238 species (e.g., SOA), whereas vehicle source $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ was a mixture of all species.

239 Additional exposure summary statistics are provided in Table 2, including means,
240 standard deviations, and pairwise correlations between components. On average, CTM
241 estimates for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ exposure were about $2 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ lower than IEG estimates, as the former
242 did not model species such as road dust and sea salt; nevertheless, all measures of total
243 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ were highly correlated ($r > 0.94$). Correlations were also high between $\text{PM}_{2.5}$
244 components, which presented difficulties in isolating independent mortality associations.
245 Each component was less correlated with remaining $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ than total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, which justified
246 including the former in mass-adjusted models.

Table 1: Cohort Summary Statistics

Characteristic	n	%
Full Cohort	164,291	100.00
Cardiopulmonary Deaths	13,732	8.36
Age (mean, std)	44.12	17.14
Sex		
Female	93,015	56.62
Male	71,276	43.38
Race-Ethnicity		
Black Non-Hispanic	25,823	15.72
Hispanic	23,128	14.08
Other/Unknown	6,892	4.19
White Non-Hispanic	108,448	66.01
Income		
\$0 - 35,000	52,713	32.09
\$35,000 - 50,000	23,934	14.57
\$50,000 - 75,000	32,689	19.90
\$75,000 and over	54,955	33.45
Marital Status		
Married	83,435	50.78
Never married	39,431	24.00
Divorced	20,462	12.45
Widowed	14,529	8.84
Separated	6,434	3.92
Educational Attainment		
< High-school Graduate	30,891	18.80
High-school Graduate	50,491	30.73
Some College	40,837	24.86
College Graduate	25,280	15.39
Post-College Graduate	16,792	10.22
BMI		
< 20	14,955	9.10
20-25	69,175	42.11
25-30	53,810	32.75
30-35	18,212	11.09
> 35	8,139	4.95
Smoking Status		
Current	41,400	25.20
Former	37,894	23.07
Never	84,997	51.74

251 **Figure 1:** Average species composition within PM_{2.5} sources. Averages were calculated
 252 after assigning individual exposures.

Table 2: Exposure Means, Standard Deviations (SD), and Pearson Correlation Coefficients ^{a, b}

	PM _{2.5}			Species						Sources				
	IEG (99-15)	IEG (01,10)	CTM (01,10)	EC	POA	SOA	SO4	NH4	NO3	EGU	Non-EGU	Vehicles	Bio	Other
Mean µg/m ³ (SD)	11.32 (1.93)	11.64 (2.28)	9.75 (2.25)	0.69 (0.20)	0.54 (0.17)	2.75 (0.71)	2.60 (0.92)	1.25 (0.42)	1.92 (0.96)	1.46 (0.90)	0.61 (0.23)	2.12 (0.97)	0.35 (0.16)	3.59 (0.90)
Correlations														
PM _{2.5}														
IEG (99-15)	1.00	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
IEG (01,10)	0.98	1.00	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
CTM (01,10)	0.95	0.95	1.00	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Species														
EC	0.70	0.69	0.72	1.00	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
POA	0.41	0.41	0.47	0.75	1.00	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SOA	0.72	0.73	0.79	0.81	0.59	1.00	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SO4	0.41	0.39	0.39	-0.05	-0.30	-0.12	1.00	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
NH4	0.80	0.80	0.84	0.35	0.11	0.37	0.75	1.00	--	--	--	--	--	--
NO3	0.71	0.74	0.77	0.65	0.56	0.78	-0.22	0.45	1.00	--	--	--	--	--
Sources														
EGU	0.30	0.29	0.31	-0.19	-0.39	-0.20	0.96	0.71	-0.24	1.00	--	--	--	--
Non-EGU	0.68	0.65	0.60	0.06	-0.11	0.14	0.73	0.80	0.25	0.70	1.00	--	--	--
Vehicles	0.73	0.74	0.77	0.86	0.69	0.89	-0.24	0.35	0.91	-0.33	0.08	1.00	--	--
Bio	0.55	0.52	0.57	0.35	0.16	0.43	0.55	0.62	0.11	0.54	0.45	0.17	1.00	--
Other	0.91	0.91	0.97	0.74	0.54	0.81	0.27	0.78	0.81	0.17	0.50	0.80	0.48	1.00
Remaining PM _{2.5}	--	--	--	0.68	0.41	0.61	-0.02	0.77	0.47	-0.09	0.52	0.47	0.52	0.92

253

254

Measures of temporal consistency and exposure modelling accuracy for PM_{2.5}

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components are reported in Table 3. For each component, temporal consistency was

256

assessed in two ways. First, by comparing the 2001 and 2010 concentration means, and

257

second, by considering the correlation between 2001 and 2010 concentrations. Temporal

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consistency was relatively low for EC and POA, suggesting that these components may

259

exhibit higher exposure measurement error. Specifically, the within component correlations

260

between 2001 and 2010 exposures was 0.78 for both EC and POA, while all other

261

component intertemporal correlations were 0.87 or higher. Exposure modelling accuracy

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was assessed through a ten-fold cross-validation (CV) R² comparison of CTM predictions

263

and ground-level monitor data. In general, exposure modelling was more accurate for

264

secondary species. For 2001 exposures, CV R² ranged from 0.63 for EC to 0.97 for SO₄.

- a. For each component, remaining PM_{2.5} was calculated as total PM_{2.5} mass minus component-specific mass.
b. All statistics were cohort-weighted, as they were calculated after assigning individual-level exposures.

265 SO₄ also had the highest CV R² for 2010 exposures, whereas organic aerosols were
 266 modelled relatively imprecisely (2010 CV R² = 0.50).

267

268 **Table 3:** Temporal Consistency^a and Accuracy^b of Predicted Exposures

Pollutant	'01 '10 Corr.	'01 Mean	'10 Mean	'01 CV R²	'10 CV R²
<u>PM_{2.5}</u>					
IEG	0.70	13.62	9.67	--	--
CTM	0.93	11.56	7.94	--	--
<u>Species</u>					
EC	0.78	0.67	0.72	0.63	0.68
POA	0.78	0.66	0.42	0.74	0.50
SOA	0.87	3.21	2.28	0.74	0.50
SO ₄	0.92	3.23	1.98	0.97	0.90
NH ₄	0.90	1.50	0.99	0.93	0.82
NO ₃	0.89	2.29	1.54	0.82	0.83
<u>Sources</u>					
EGU	0.96	1.95	0.96	--	--
Non-EGU	0.97	0.70	0.52	--	--
Vehicles	0.98	2.66	1.58	--	--
Bio	0.92	0.36	0.35	--	--
Other	0.90	4.14	3.03	--	--

269

270 *Mortality Risk Analysis:*

271 Single-pollutant HRs, per unit µg/m³ (panel A) and per relative mean µg/m³ (panel B),
 272 are displayed in Figure 2. Numeric equivalents of these estimates, along with HRs scaled per
 273 interquartile range, are reported in Table S2. In single-pollutant models, there were positive,
 274 significant (p < 0.05) mortality associations for PM_{2.5} mass and each component, except
 275 POA. Relative effect sizes differed between scaling methods, as each approach answers a
 276 distinct question. When scaled per unit, HRs provide information about per mass
 277 concentration harmfulness, whereas scaling per mean reflects a component's aggregate
 278 contribution to mortality risk.

- a. Measures of temporal consistency included cohort-weighted annual exposure means (e.g., '01 Mean) and Pearson correlation coefficients between 2001 and 2010 exposures (i.e., '01 '10 Corr.).
- b. Exposure accuracy was measured through a ten-fold cross validation (CV) R² comparison of predicted concentrations and ground-level monitor observations.

279 Per unit $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (panel A), single-pollutant HRs were relatively large for EC, non-EGU,
 280 and bio. These differences are difficult to interpret due to confounding from correlation with
 281 total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$. That is, in single-pollutant models components with higher correlation with total
 282 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ likely exhibit a larger positive bias. Moreover, this bias is greater for components with
 283 lower exposure means (e.g., EC, non-EGU, bio) when estimates are scaled per unit $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

284 **Figure 2:** Single-pollutant hazards ratios and 95% confidence intervals (CI) per unit $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
 285 (panel A) and per relative mean $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (panel B) increase in exposure

286
 287 Scaling single-pollutant HRs per mean increase in exposure (panel B) partially accounts
 288 for this problem, while allowing estimates to reflect a component's relative contribution to
 289 total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ exposure. Of the three estimates of total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ exposure, the seventeen-year
 290 average (i.e., 1999-2015) of IEG-modelled $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ was associated with the largest increase in

291 mortality risk (HR = 1.41; 95% CI [1.26, 1.56]; per 11.32 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). Despite having a similar
 292 mean exposure, the estimated HR for the two-year average (i.e., 2001 and 2010) of IEG-
 293 modelled PM_{2.5} was 26% smaller (HR = 1.30; 95% CI [1.19, 1.43]; per 11.64 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) than its
 294 seventeen-year counterpart. This suggests that assigning component exposures as the
 295 average of two annual concentrations resulted in conservative mortality risk estimates.
 296 Among PM_{2.5} components, EC (HR = 1.27; 95% CI [1.18, 1.37]; per 0.69 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and SOA
 297 (HR = 1.30; 95% CI [1.20, 1.41]; per 2.75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) had the highest HRs per relative mean
 298 increase in exposure.

299

300

301 **Figure 3:** parameter estimates (i.e., natural log of hazard ratio) and 95% confidence
 302 intervals (CI) from single-pollutant models plotted according to component correlation with
 303 PM_{2.5} mass. Estimates are relative to a component mean increase in exposure.

304

305 To account for bias from correlation between component and total PM_{2.5} exposure,
 306 Figure 3 plots single-pollutant parameter estimates (i.e., natural log of HR) according to
 307 component correlation with PM_{2.5} mass. The plotted diagonal provides a baseline
 308 comparison by indicating the effect size one would expect to see solely from component
 309 correlation with PM_{2.5} exposure. Thus, distance from the plotted diagonal serves as a basic

310 metric for whether single-pollutant mortality associations are relatively high or low. As
311 such, Figure 3 provides some indication that EC, SOA, and SO₄ have relatively high single-
312 pollutant associations with cardiopulmonary mortality.

313 While Figure 3 is useful for interpreting single-pollutant estimates, a more thorough
314 attempt at estimating component-specific mortality associations is to explicitly control for
315 remaining mass. Figure 4 plots HRs from mass-adjusted models, which included a given
316 PM_{2.5} component (black circle point estimates) and remaining PM_{2.5} mass (white square
317 point estimates). Estimates are reported per unit $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to reflect relative toxicities. Numeric
318 equivalents of these estimates are provided in Table S3.

319 For several components, controlling for remaining PM_{2.5} reduced the magnitude of
320 single-pollutant HRs. Specifically, for POA, SO₄, NH₄, EGU, and non-EGU, positive single-
321 pollutant risk estimates became either null or negative after controlling for remaining PM_{2.5}.
322 In contrast, EC maintained an elevated HR when controlling for remaining mass (HR =
323 1.36; 95% CI [1.12, 1.64]; per unit $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), with risk estimates ten times greater than total
324 PM_{2.5} (per unit $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). Similarly, SOA mortality risk estimates remained large after
325 controlling for remaining mass (HR = 1.11; 95% CI [1.05, 1.17]; per unit $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). For PM_{2.5}
326 sources, controlling for remaining mass generally reduced the magnitude of single-pollutant
327 HRs, except for vehicle sources. That is, vehicle source HRs were nearly identical in single-
328 pollutant (HR = 1.07; 95% CI [1.05, 1.10]; per unit $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and mass-adjusted models (HR =
329 1.06; 95% CI [1.03, 1.10]; per unit $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$).

330 **Figure 4:** Remaining PM_{2.5} mass adjusted hazard ratios (HRs) and 95% confidence intervals
 331 (CI) per unit $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. For each component, a separate model was specified to include two
 332 pollutants: the component (black circle point estimates) and remaining PM_{2.5} mass (i.e., total
 333 PM_{2.5} minus component) (white square point estimates). Stars reflect p-values from a
 334 hypothesis test with the null hypothesis that component and remaining PM_{2.5} HRs were
 335 equivalent (* $p < 0.10$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$).

336 In Figure 4, component HRs are plotted adjacent to remaining PM_{2.5} mass HRs to
337 facilitate a comparison of relative toxicities. For species, both EC and SOA had higher HRs
338 than their remaining PM_{2.5} mass. A formal hypothesis test revealed that these differences
339 were statistically significant, with p-values of 0.004 and 0.005 for EC and SOA respectively.
340 Source-specific HRs were generally lower than HRs for remaining mass. However, the HR
341 for vehicle source pollution was significantly larger (p = 0.03) than its respective remaining
342 mass term.

343 In addition to component-specific HRs, an aim of this analysis was to estimate mortality
344 associations for primary and secondary PM_{2.5}. Figure 5 plots single-pollutant (black point
345 estimates) and two-pollutant HRs (red point estimates) for primary (circle point estimates)
346 and secondary species (diamond point estimates) from total PM_{2.5}, vehicles, and “other”
347 sources. Estimates are reported per unit (panel A) and per mean $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (panel B) increase in
348 exposure. Numeric equivalents of these estimates are provided in Table S4.

349 Per unit $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, single-pollutant HRs were consistently larger for primary species. This
350 was likely due to confounding from correlated components, as the same did not hold in two-
351 pollutant specifications. In two-pollutant models, HRs were similar for total primary and
352 total secondary PM_{2.5}, as well as for primary and secondary PM_{2.5} from vehicle sources. For
353 “other” sources, the primary PM_{2.5} HR was significantly smaller, as “other” source primary
354 PM_{2.5} was predominantly POA (see Figure 1).

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Figure 5: Hazard ratios and 95% confidence intervals (CI) for primary (circle point estimates) and secondary species (diamond point estimates) within PM_{2.5} sources. Single-pollutant models (black point estimates) included one pollutant (e.g., primary vehicles), whereas two-pollutant models (red point estimates) included both primary and secondary species from a given source (e.g., primary vehicles and secondary vehicles). Estimates are reported per unit $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (panel A) and per mean $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (panel B) increase in exposure.

When scaled per mean, HRs for primary and secondary PM_{2.5} from vehicle sources were nearly identical, in both single-pollutant and two-pollutant specifications. In contrast, for total PM_{2.5} and “other” sources, HRs were larger for secondary species. Specifically, in a two-pollutant model, the HR for secondary total PM_{2.5} (HR = 1.26; 95% CI [1.12, 1.41]; per 8.52 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) was significantly larger ($p = 0.05$) than for primary total PM_{2.5} (HR = 1.01; 95% CI [0.89, 1.14]; per 1.23 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). While this can be attributed to higher exposure levels for

369 secondary species, it does suggest that secondary PM_{2.5} contributes more than primary PM_{2.5}
370 to actualized risk of cardiopulmonary mortality.

371 Measures of model fit from single-pollutant models, along with two additional
372 specifications that included all species (six pollutants) or all sources (five pollutants)
373 simultaneously, are provided in Table S5. IEG estimates fit mortality outcomes better than
374 CTM estimates of total PM_{2.5} exposure. Single-pollutant models for EC, SOA, and vehicles
375 fit mortality better than both (i.e., IEG and CTM) two-year averages of PM_{2.5}, but not the
376 seventeen-year average of IEG-modelled PM_{2.5}. Including all species or all sources
377 separately did not improve model fit over aggregate PM_{2.5} specifications.

378

379 **Discussion**

380 In this analysis, there were positive, significant ($p < 0.05$) single-pollutant mortality
381 associations for PM_{2.5} and all components, except POA. While most associations became
382 insignificant after controlling for remaining PM_{2.5}, we found evidence that EC, SOA, and
383 vehicle sources are important contributors to risk of cardiopulmonary mortality.

384

385 *Species:*

386 Of the considered components, we found that EC was associated with the largest increase
387 in cardiopulmonary mortality risk (per unit $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), with and without controlling for
388 remaining PM_{2.5}. Moreover, in a mass-adjusted model the HR for EC was significantly
389 larger ($p = 0.004$) than for remaining PM_{2.5} mass.

390 In past studies, EC has shown elevated single-pollutant mortality associations that lose
391 significance after adjusting for other pollutants.^{9, 32, 33} A previous analysis of the American

392 Cancer Society (ACS) cohort estimated eight times greater cardiopulmonary mortality risk
393 for EC than PM_{2.5} in single-pollutant models (per unit $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), with EC HRs substantially
394 reduced and insignificant in multi-pollutant models.³² Similarly, in the California Teacher's
395 Study (CTS) cohort, Ostro et al.⁹ found that significant ($p < 0.05$), single-pollutant EC
396 mortality associations became insignificant after adjusting for NO₃.

397 Instability in the EC mortality association has been attributed to EC's complex,
398 heterogenous nature.^{9, 34} Specifically, high spatial variation presents difficulties in accurately
399 modeling EC exposures. While EC was modelled relatively imprecisely (see Table 3), we
400 observed significant EC HRs when controlling for remaining PM_{2.5}, providing some
401 evidence that EC has a direct relationship with cardiopulmonary mortality.

402 In addition to EC, our results suggest that SOA may be a key contributor to the PM_{2.5}
403 mortality relationship. That is, in a mass-adjusted model the HR for SOA was significantly
404 larger ($p = 0.005$) than for remaining PM_{2.5} (per unit $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). Similarly, in the CTS cohort
405 anthropogenic SOA was significantly ($p < 0.05$) associated with ischemic heart disease
406 (IHD) mortality in single-pollutant models.⁹ Moreover, they found that mortality
407 associations for anthropogenic SOA in the ultrafine range remained significant in all
408 combinations of two-pollutant models.⁹ Short-term analyses have found similar results, with
409 a study in Xi'an, China reporting significant cardiovascular and respiratory mortality
410 associations for organic carbon, with and without adjusting for PM_{2.5} mass.³⁵

411 While EC and SOA maintained relatively high HRs, single-pollutant mortality
412 associations for SO₄ vanished after controlling for remaining PM_{2.5}, suggesting that SO₄ is,
413 at least in part, a tracer of other harmful pollutants. SO₄, along with its precursor SO₂, has
414 been significantly associated with mortality in several observational cohort studies,^{32, 36}

415 including some of the earliest to consider speciated PM_{2.5}.^{7, 37} However, the plausibility of a
416 causal link between SO₄ and mortality is not supported by toxicology studies, which
417 collectively report minimal biological potency in humans or animals at environmentally
418 relevant levels.³⁸ Thus, observational associations could represent the mortality relationship
419 of particulate species and co-pollutants correlated with SO₄, not SO₄ alone.³²

420 Similarly, mortality associations were relatively low for POA and NH₄, as exposures
421 were inversely associated with cardiopulmonary mortality risk in mass-adjusted models.
422 With high correlations between remaining and total PM_{2.5}, mass-adjusted HRs could reflect
423 changes in the PM_{2.5} composition, not an aggregate decrease in PM_{2.5} exposure. Specifically,
424 inverse NH₄ and POA mortality associations could represent a decrease in average PM_{2.5}
425 toxicity when the fractional PM_{2.5} composition has larger proportions of these species.
426 Alternatively, inverse NH₄ and POA mortality associations could be the result of statistical
427 noise or some unobserved confounder. In any case, it remains unlikely that exposure to NH₄
428 or POA decreases risk of cardiopulmonary mortality.

429

430 *Sources:*

431 While each considered source was significantly ($p < 0.05$) associated with mortality in
432 single-pollutant models, only vehicle sources remained significant after adjusting for
433 remaining PM_{2.5} mass. In mass-adjusted models, the estimated increase in cardiopulmonary
434 mortality risk from exposure to vehicle source PM_{2.5} was eight times greater (per unit
435 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) than from remaining PM_{2.5} mass. This difference was statistically significant ($p =$
436 0.03) when formally testing for equality of vehicle source and remaining PM_{2.5} HRs.

437 Past analyses have supported a relationship between mortality and long-term exposure to
438 vehicle source PM_{2.5}, although uncertainty remains due to a limited number of studies.³⁹ In
439 the CTS cohort, there were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) single-pollutant associations
440 between IHD mortality and four subgroups of vehicle source PM_{2.5}.⁹ Short-term analyses
441 have also reported significant associations between adverse health effects and vehicle source
442 PM_{2.5}. An analysis in Barcelona, Spain found that traffic related PM_{2.5} was associated with a
443 more than 8% increase in daily cardiovascular mortality (per 9.7 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ with 2-day lag), in
444 single and multi-source models.⁴⁰ Similarly, a U.S. study found that 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of mobile
445 source PM_{2.5} increased daily mortality by 3.4%.⁴¹ In addition to daily mortality, a series of
446 short-term studies in New York State found that vehicle source PM_{2.5} was significantly
447 associated with hospitalizations and emergency department visits for influenza, cardiac
448 arrhythmia, ischemic stroke, and congestive heart failure.^{42, 43} These studies, combined with
449 the present analysis, provide suggestive evidence that vehicle sources are an important
450 contributor to the PM_{2.5} morbidity and mortality relationship.

451

452 *Primary vs. Secondary:*

453 Estimating the relative mortality associations of primary and secondary PM_{2.5} yielded
454 little insight beyond what can be explained by component-specific mortality associations
455 and differences in exposure means. That is, differences in source-specific primary and
456 secondary mortality associations were driven either by the species composition within
457 source (see Figure 3) or relative exposure means. Ultimately, our results suggest that
458 mortality associations differ more within primary and secondary designations (e.g., EC vs.
459 POA) than between primary and secondary designations (e.g., primary vehicles vs.

460 secondary vehicles). Nevertheless, with a significantly larger HR per mean exposure, total
461 secondary PM_{2.5} likely contributes more than total primary PM_{2.5} to actualized risk of
462 cardiopulmonary mortality.

463

464 *Limitations:*

465 An inherent limitation of observational air pollution analyses is imperfect assignment of
466 pollution exposures. In our analysis, individuals were assigned an MSA-level average of
467 2001 and 2010 concentration estimates, as a proxy for lifetime exposure. Assigning lifetime
468 exposure as the average of two annual estimates fails to account for the temporal complexity
469 of component levels and composition. However, we found that intertemporal correlations for
470 PM_{2.5} components were consistently high ($r > 0.78$), which suggests that incorporating
471 additional years of CTM exposure estimates would provide only marginal improvements in
472 exposure accuracy. If anything, using the average of 2001 and 2010 concentrations resulted
473 in conservative mortality risk estimates. For a thorough analysis on the influence of
474 temporal exposure windows in the NHIS cohort, see Lefler et al.³¹

475 Additionally, NHIS public-use residential data included only MSA of residence, which
476 required assigning exposures at the MSA level. For this reason, along with the 36-kilometer
477 resolution in the CTM, we were unable to account for local variations in PM_{2.5} components.
478 This is particularly problematic for components with high spatial variability, such as EC.

479 Another limitation is that differences in component mortality associations could have
480 been driven by statistical factors aside from toxicity. As previously mentioned, exposure
481 modelling accuracy, observed variation, and component intercorrelation all affect the
482 precision and magnitude of mortality risk estimates. While these factors vary between

483 components, they are likely independent of relative toxicity. Thus, differences in effect size
484 and statistical significance could simply reflect varying statistical advantages, not
485 differential mortality associations.

486 A final limitation is potential confounding from unobserved or inadequately controlled
487 for risk factors. If correlated with pollution and cardiopulmonary mortality, unobserved
488 characteristics such as dietary habits, physical activity, and climate could have resulted in
489 spurious findings. Additionally, dynamic risk factors such as smoking status, BMI, income,
490 and residence were reported only at time of survey, providing an imperfect measure of the
491 lifetime pathway of these variables.

492 Notwithstanding these limitations, our findings suggest that there are differences in
493 mortality associations across PM_{2.5} species and sources. These differences appear to be
494 driven by factors other than whether PM_{2.5} is primary or secondary. After controlling for
495 remaining PM_{2.5}, the mortality association for EC was ten times greater (per unit $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)
496 than for total PM_{2.5}. Similarly, SOA and vehicle sources had significantly larger HRs than
497 remaining PM_{2.5} mass (per unit $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). These findings suggest that targeted abatement
498 strategies could be more beneficial to public health than simply reducing total PM_{2.5}. If
499 corroborated in other studies, this analysis could help inform a targeted, efficient approach
500 to reducing air pollution mortality.

501

502

Supporting Information Figure and Table Descriptions

503

Table S1: Breakdown of Cardiopulmonary Mortality by ICD 10 Codes

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Figure S1: Illustration of Pollution Exposures across NHIS Surveyed MSAs

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Table S2: Numeric Single-Pollutant Hazard Ratios (95% Confidence Intervals)

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Table S3: Numeric Mass-Adjusted Hazard Ratios (95% Confidence Intervals)

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Table S4: Numeric Hazard Ratios (95% Confidence Intervals) for Primary and Secondary

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Species within PM_{2.5} Source

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Table S5: Measures of Model Fit

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